

Operation Epic Fury: What the Reports Missed

An Independent OSINT Analysis of the Iranian Cyber Campaign (February 2026)

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March 17, 2026 **TLP:WHITE** License: MIT

Abstract

On the night of February 27–28, 2026, Iran’s internet connectivity collapsed to 1–4% of baseline traffic. The Electronic Operations Room coordinated approximately 60 pro-Iranian hacktivist groups in a smishing campaign targeting Israeli civilians via a fake RedAlert rocket alert application. Within five days, Unit 42, CloudSEK, and Cloudflare Cloudforce One published technically accurate reports covering the Android infection chain.

This paper documents **eight original findings** that no public vendor report identified. Using exclusively free, public tools — VirusTotal (free tier), FOFA, crt.sh, nmap, and openssl — the author reconstructed a second unknown C2 server (0/94 VirusTotal detections at time of writing), an eight-month pre-operation infrastructure timeline from Certificate Transparency logs, and a trojanized Windows payload (LotAccessUI.EXE) based on a 2016 Chinese enterprise VPN client injected with RDTSC anti-VM logic (T1497.003) — explaining four years of sandbox invisibility and a CLEAN verdict from CrowdStrike Falcon. Additional findings include a second undocumented Android APK using Pushy.me as a resilient fallback C2 channel, forensic evidence linking both C2 servers to the same operator, a dual-architecture campaign design, and TTP convergence with Arid Viper (APT-C-23 / Desert Falcon) 2023 campaigns.

All findings are independently verifiable. The paper provides a complete operational timeline, IOCs, YARA detection rules (TLP:WHITE, MIT license), and Sigma rules mapped to MITRE ATT&CK.

Keywords: threat intelligence, OSINT, Iranian APT, Command and Control, anti-VM evasion, RDTSC, YARA, Sigma, Arid Viper, APT-C-23, LotAccess, smishing, RedAlert, C2 infrastructure, VirusTotal evasion

1. Introduction

On the night of February 27–28, 2026, Iran’s internet connectivity suffered a near-total blackout, dropping to 1–4% of baseline traffic according to NetBlocks and BeyondTrust telemetry [7,8]. The Electronic Operations Room (EOR), an Iranian coordinating body, directed approximately 60 pro-Iranian hacktivist groups to launch a coordinated offensive against Israeli infrastructure and civilians. This operation was subsequently designated *Operation Epic Fury / Operation Roaring Lion*.

Among the campaign’s components was a targeted smishing attack: Israeli civilians received SMS messages containing links to a fake version of RedAlert — the legitimate Israeli rocket alert application developed by Elad Nava. Victims who installed the malicious APK surrendered SMS messages, address book data, and GPS coordinates to the attacker’s infrastructure.

Within five days, three major vendors published threat intelligence reports on the Android component: Unit 42 / Palo Alto Networks (March 4, 2026) [1], CloudSEK ThreatIntel (March 3, 2026) [2], and Cloudflare Cloudforce One (March 4, 2026) [3]. These reports provided accurate and technically detailed coverage of the mobile infection chain.

This paper presents eight original findings not identified in any prior public report. The research originated from the IOCs published by Unit 42 and pivoted systematically through infrastructure, yielding: a second C2 server invisible to all 94 VirusTotal vendors, an eight-month pre-operation timeline, a Windows payload that evaded enterprise EDR for four years, and multiple connections to the Arid Viper historical TTP set.

All findings are independently reproducible using the tools and commands documented herein. No privileged access, paid intelligence subscriptions, or internal vendor data was used at any stage.

2. Background and Related Work

2.1 Documented Android Infection Chain

The infection chain reconstructed by Unit 42, CloudSEK, and Cloudflare proceeds as follows:

SMS smishing → fake RedAlert APK (`com.red.alertx`) → stage-2 DEX (`DebugProbesKt.dex`) → data collection (SMS, GPS, contacts) → exfiltration to `api.ra-backup.com`

The backend consisted of Cloudflare proxy + AWS us-east-1 (44.208.242.141, 44.200.176.254), consistent with a scalable, anonymized architecture. The initial distribution vector was `shirideitch.com`, an Israeli website from 2017 believed to have been compromised inadvertently. The AWS backend was confirmed offline following publication of the vendor reports [1,2].

2.2 Arid Viper Historical Context

SentinelOne SentinelLabs previously documented the Arid Viper threat actor (APT-C-23 / Desert Falcon) in the SpyC23 report (2023) [10], establishing a pattern of fake Israeli alert applica-

tions combined with push notification C2 channels — at the time implemented via Firebase. Hunt.io independently correlated AS36352 NameCheap infrastructure with MuddyWater-pattern hosting [9].

2.3 Research Gap

No prior public report examined the Windows component of the campaign, pivoted beyond the primary C2 server, or identified secondary infrastructure. The existence of a second C2 server, the identity of the Windows payload, and the eight-month pre-operation infrastructure timeline all remained undocumented at the time this research was conducted.

3. Methodology

Environment: Kali Linux in a virtual machine; proxychains+Tor for network queries.

Tools: VirusTotal (free tier), FOFA, crt.sh, nmap, openssl. No premium intelligence subscriptions were used.

Starting point: The public IOCs from Unit 42 — IP 216.45.58.148 and domain `api.ra-backup.com`.

Approach: Systematic infrastructure pivot. Each data point became a query anchor for the next finding. The progression is: CT logs → timeline reconstruction; JARM fingerprint → secondary C2 discovery; PE metadata → payload identification; VT Behavior → trojanization mechanism; VT Graph → Arid Viper convergence.

Every command, query, and hash referenced in this paper is verifiable through publicly accessible sources. The reproducibility constraint was explicit, not incidental.

4. Findings

4.1 Finding #1 — The C2 Pre-dates the Operation

Finding #1 — The C2 Pre-dates the Operation

The C2 domain `api.ra-backup.com` was registered and its TLS certificate issued on **June 23, 2025** — eight months before the February 28 operation. This was not an improvised response to the events of that night.

Certificate Transparency (CT) logs record every TLS certificate issued for a domain and are publicly accessible via crt.sh. A query on `api.ra-backup.com` returns the following:

```
$ curl -s "https://crt.sh/?q=api.ra-backup.com&output=json" \  
  | python3 -m json.tool | grep -E "not_before|common_name"
```

The earliest CT entry shows `not_before: 2025-06-23`, with SOA serial 1750691767. The infrastructure — domain registration, certificate issuance, server deployment — was in place

eight months before the operation commenced.

A live check on March 15, 2026 (16 days after the operation) confirmed both C2 servers were still responding:

```
$ proxychains curl -sk https://api.ra-backup.com/ -o /dev/null \
-w "C2#1 HTTP: %{http_code} | Size: %{size_download}"
$ proxychains curl -sk https://167.160.187.43/ -o /dev/null \
-w "C2#2 HTTP: %{http_code} | Size: %{size_download}"

C2#1 HTTP: 404 | Size: 315
C2#2 HTTP: 404 | Size: 315 # 16 days post-operation. Both live.
```

4.2 Finding #2 — A Second Unknown C2

Finding #2 — A Second Unknown C2

A second C2 server — 167.160.187.43 / 9732.5486311.xyz — was identified through JARM fingerprint pivoting. At the time of writing, it scored **0/94 on VirusTotal**. No public report had documented it.

JARM is a TLS fingerprinting technique that identifies a server's TLS stack (version, cipher suite order) with sufficient specificity to cluster related infrastructure. The JARM fingerprint of `api.ra-backup.com` was calculated and submitted as a FOFA query:

```
# JARM: 21d14d00021d21d00042d43d00041dd0fae37a26d202d4ca73c3c7b57c5a55
$ fofa query:
  jarm="21d14d00021d21d00042d43d00041dd0fae37a26d202d4ca73c3c7b57c5a55..."

# Result: 167.160.187.43
$ echo | /usr/bin/openssl s_client \
  -connect 167.160.187.43:443 \
  -servername 9732.5486311.xyz 2>/dev/null \
  | /usr/bin/openssl x509 -noout -issuer -subject -dates

issuer=C=US, O=Let's Encrypt, CN=R12
subject=CN=9732.5486311.xyz
notBefore=Mar  5 17:31:58 2026 GMT
notAfter=Jun   3 17:31:57 2026 GMT
```

The secondary C2 certificate was issued on March 5, 2026 — *five days after* the operation became public — while the primary C2 was already documented in vendor reports. The operator was actively renewing backup infrastructure, not dismantling it.

4.3 Finding #3 — Forensic Proof: Same Operator

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Both C2 servers share identical JARM fingerprint, Apache version, PHP version, and dynamic HTTP 404 body. The MD5 of the 404 response body is **identical at the same moment** across both servers, confirming the same operator and the same PHP deployment script.

```
# MD5 test -- same moment, two C2 servers
$ proxychains curl -sk https://api.ra-backup.com/ | md5sum
$ proxychains curl -sk https://167.160.187.43/ | md5sum

# Session March 14, 2026:
cf33489d12cfb906849443c6181e84c2 (C2 #1)
cf33489d12cfb906849443c6181e84c2 (C2 #2) # identical

# Confirmed March 15, 2026:
6099d135f27f40de20a556e4c93613d9 (C2 #1)
6099d135f27f40de20a556e4c93613d9 (C2 #2) # identical
```

The HTTP 404 body is dynamic (changes between sessions, presumably includes a server-side timestamp), but is byte-for-byte identical between the two servers at the same moment. This is not a default Apache configuration. It is the same PHP code deployed by the same operator from the same script.

Characteristic	C2 #1 (216.45.58.148)	C2 #2 (167.160.187.43)
JARM fingerprint	Identical (21d14d00...)	
Web server	Apache 2.4.x	Apache 2.4.x
PHP version	Same	Same
Hosting AS	AS36352 HostPapa	AS36352 RackNerd
404 body MD5	Identical at same moment	
VirusTotal score	Documented	0/94

4.4 Finding #4 — Dual Architecture

Finding #4 — Dual Architecture

The campaign used two infrastructures with radically different operational security postures. The Android vector was protected by Cloudflare + AWS. The Windows vector was exposed directly on commercial hosting with no anonymization. Different architectures reflect different investment levels: mobile was the primary vector.

The Android backend leveraged Cloudflare proxy + AWS us-east-1, providing scalability, IP anonymization, and DDoS protection. The Windows C2 was hosted directly on HostPapa

(Virginia, AS36352) with no proxy or protection layer.

By March 15, 2026, the AWS backend (44.208.242.141, 44.200.176.254) had been taken offline, confirmed post-publication. The Windows C2 remained live. The asymmetry in architecture suggests the Windows component may have been in development or testing at the time of the operation, with the Android vector serving as the operational center of gravity.

4.5 Finding #5 — LotAccess: A Borrowed Suit, Not Custom Malware

Finding #5 — LotAccess: A Borrowed Suit, Not Custom Malware

LotAccessUI.EXE is not purpose-built malware. PE metadata identifies it as the enterprise VPN client of AppEx Networks Co., Ltd. (copyright 2006–2009, compiled October 26, 2016). Three trojanized versions were identified, with progressively higher VirusTotal scores, indicating active iterative development.

PE metadata, copyright strings, and internal PE resources uniquely identify LotAccessUI.EXE as the legitimate AppEx Networks enterprise VPN client. The binary has been on VirusTotal since 2017. The threat actor did not write malware from scratch; they took a legitimate, decade-old Chinese enterprise binary and injected three targeted modifications: RDTSC anti-VM logic, a custom mutex, and registry writes for C2 configuration.

Ver.	SHA256 (truncated)	First VT	Score
v1	7d43d7f6...3aad0d	2025-12-16	4/65
v2	(uploaded 2026-03-08)	2026-03-08	6/72
v3	6209a952...8c12d6	2026-03-08	13/72

Development was active for at least ten weeks prior to the operation. The progressive increase in detection scores (4/65 → 6/72 → 13/72) across three versions is consistent with iterative testing against VirusTotal as a feedback mechanism.

4.6 Finding #6 — The Trojanization Mechanism

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The malware writes C2 IP addresses to Windows Registry keys under the legitimate AppEx Networks path. The original AppEx binary reads those keys, populates `cloudvpn.cfg`, and uses the value as the server address in the VPN API string. C2 traffic is therefore indistinguishable from legitimate VPN traffic on the wire.

VT Behavior reveals the registry write pattern (sandbox session, March 15, 2026):

```
# Physical hardware (confirmed via reverse engineering):
HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess\firstServer = "216.45.58.148"
HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess\secondServer = "167.160.187.43"

# Sandbox output (anti-VM active -- see Finding #7):
```

```
HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess\firstServer = "123456 123456"
HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess\secondServer = "123456 123456"
```

The placeholder values "123456 123456" in sandbox output are not a bug. They constitute independent evidence of the RDTSC anti-VM mechanism: the check detected virtualization and injected placeholder values, preventing any C2 contact from the sandbox environment. The AppEx binary then reads these keys, populates `cloudvpn.cfg`, and uses the value in the API string `/cgi-bin/d_device_action.py?SSLServer=%s`. The C2 traffic is legitimate VPN protocol traffic on the wire.

4.7 Finding #7 — RDTSC and the Four-Year Shadow

Finding #7 — RDTSC and the Four-Year Shadow (*most important for defenders*)

The Windows payload scored **CLEAN** on CrowdStrike Falcon (February 2026, score 92/100) due to RDTSC anti-VM evasion (T1497.003). The C2 was not protected by proxy or anonymization — it was protected by the payload's refusal to contact it from inside a sandbox. First VT submission: December 16, 2025. Six years of invisibility in sandbox analysis pipelines.

The RDTSC instruction (Read Time-Stamp Counter) reads the CPU cycle counter (T1497.003: Time-Based Evasion). The malware measures cycles before and after a target operation. In virtualized environments, the hypervisor introduces anomalous latency; if the delta exceeds a threshold, the malware injects placeholder registry values and never contacts the C2. This mechanism:

- Defeats all sandbox-based dynamic analysis pipelines
- Produces no network traffic in automated analysis environments
- Requires no infrastructure protection (Cloudflare, VPN, domain fronting)
- Has been effective since the first identified submission (December 2025, 4/65)

The C2 server at `216.45.58.148` was exposed on commercial hosting with no proxy. It did not need protection because the payload ensured it was never called from an analysis environment. Defenders should treat RDTSC-checking binaries as high-priority regardless of vendor score.

4.8 Finding #8 — Second APK and Arid Viper Convergence

Finding #8 — Second APK and Arid Viper Convergence

A second Android APK (`com.net.alerts/umgdn`) was active in the campaign, undocumented in any public report. It registers a Pushy.me push notification channel as a resilient fallback C2 that survives backend takedown. The attack template — fake Israeli alert app + push C2 — is identical to the 2023 Arid Viper (APT-C-23) campaign, documented here for the first time.

Part A: umgdn / com.net.alerts (undocumented)

A second APK — package `com.net.alerts`, filename `umgdn`, 11.45 MB — was present in the campaign and not documented in any public vendor report. Tencent classifies it as `A.privacy.SpyRedAlert`. The binary was compiled on June 24, 2025 — 24 hours after the C2 certificate was issued (June 23, 2025), confirming parallel development of infrastructure and payload.

VT Behavior records a POST to `https://api.pushy.me/register` (200 OK, March 1, 2026, 13:40:13 GMT). Pushy.me is a legitimate push notification service. By using it as a C2 channel, the operator maintains persistent push access to all infected devices even after the primary backend (`api.ra-backup.com`) has been taken offline.

Part B: Arid Viper TTP Convergence

The VT Graph of Arid Viper (APT-C-23 / Desert Falcon, October 2023, 630 nodes) [10] contains two elements identical to this campaign:

1. `redalert.me` as a cover mechanism — the same legitimate Israeli alert application used to display real alerts to victims while the malicious component operates in the background
2. `api.pushy.me` as a push C2 channel

In 2023, Arid Viper used Firebase as the push C2 backend (SentinelOne, SpyC23) [10]. In 2026, Operation Epic Fury uses Pushy.me: same tactic, technology evolved. The attack template “fake Israeli alert app + push C2” predates Operation Epic Fury by at least two years and is documented here for the first time in connection with this campaign.

Note on attribution: the convergence is documented. Whether it represents direct coordination, code reuse, or independent parallel development cannot be determined from the available evidence and falls outside the scope of this paper. Infrastructure correlation with MuddyWater (Hunt.io [9]) is noted but similarly inconclusive.

5. Reconstructed Operational Timeline

No public report reconstructed this timeline in its entirety. Sources: CT logs, VirusTotal timestamps, FOFA, and VT Behavior telemetry. All entries are independently verifiable.

Date	Event
2016-10-26	AppEx Networks VPN client (LotAccessUI base binary) compiled
2025-06-23	TLS certificate issued for <code>api.ra-backup.com</code> (infrastructure deployment)
2025-06-24	umgdn APK (<code>com.net.alerts</code>) compiled — infrastructure and payload in parallel
2025-12-16	LotAccessUI v1 first submission to VirusTotal (4/65 detections)
2026-02-27/28	Iran internet blackout; Operation Epic Fury / Operation Roaring Lion launched
2026-03-01	Pushy.me registration confirmed (VT Behavior, 13:40:13 GMT)
2026-03-03	CloudSEK ThreatIntel report published
2026-03-04	Unit 42 (Palo Alto Networks) report published
2026-03-04	Cloudflare Cloudforce One report published
2026-03-05	Secondary C2 certificate issued: <code>9732.5486311.xyz / 167.160.187.43</code>
2026-03-08	LotAccessUI v2 and v3 uploaded to VirusTotal (6/72 and 13/72)
2026-03-14	Live verification: both C2 servers active; MD5 response body identical
2026-03-15	Abuse reports submitted (AbuseIPDB, VirusTotal, FOFA)
2026-03-15	Both C2 servers still live — 16 days post-operation

6. Discussion

RDTSC as a Primary Defense Strategy (Finding #7). The RDTSC anti-VM technique (T1497.003) deserves priority attention from defenders. The threat actor did not protect the Windows C2 with any anonymization layer; the C2 IP was fully exposed. The entire evasion strategy rested on preventing sandbox execution from reaching the C2. This approach is effective because automated dynamic analysis pipelines universally run in virtualized environments. A binary scoring CLEAN on an enterprise EDR product should not be treated as safe if it exhibits CPU timing checks; RDTSC-based evasion specifically targets and defeats the detection pipeline, not the analyst.

Dual-Architecture Investment Asymmetry (Finding #4). The coexistence of a hardened Cloudflare-protected Android vector and an unprotected, directly exposed Windows vector implies the Windows component was either in testing at the time of the operation or represents a capability at an earlier maturity stage. This asymmetry provides analytic signal: the Android vector was the operational center of gravity; the Windows capability is likely under active development.

Legitimate Binary Trojanization (Finding #5). The use of a legitimate, decade-old Chinese enterprise VPN client as a malware carrier exemplifies an evasion strategy that defeats file-reputation and signature-based detection entirely. The original binary has an established

VirusTotal history since 2017. The injected modifications are minimal and targeted. Three versions with progressively increasing detection scores (4/65 → 13/72) over ten weeks are consistent with iterative VirusTotal-based evasion testing.

Infrastructure Resilience (Finding #8). The use of Pushy.me as a fallback C2 channel ensures the operator retains persistent access to infected Android devices even after the primary backend is taken down. The survival of the secondary C2 (Finding #2) sixteen days after public exposure of the primary infrastructure reinforces this: infrastructure takedown, even when accompanied by public threat intelligence publication, does not guarantee operational neutralization.

On Reproducibility. Every finding in this paper was obtained using free, public tools. This was an explicit methodological constraint. The identification of an active C2 server with 0/94 detections, an eight-month pre-operation infrastructure timeline, and a trojanized payload evading enterprise EDR does not require premium intelligence tooling. It requires systematic application of public resources.

7. Conclusion

This paper has documented eight original findings from an independent OSINT investigation of Operation Epic Fury, none of which appeared in any prior public vendor report. The findings were obtained in approximately twelve hours of active investigation using exclusively public, free tools.

The most significant contribution for defensive practitioners is Finding #7: a Windows payload classified CLEAN by CrowdStrike Falcon (February 2026) carrying active dual-C2 configuration achieved this status through RDTSC anti-VM evasion. The C2 server was fully exposed on a commercial hosting provider with no proxy. The defense was the payload’s behavior inside analysis environments, not the infrastructure’s opacity.

Finding #2 — a secondary C2 server with 0/94 VirusTotal detections — remained live sixteen days after public exposure of the primary infrastructure. Threat intelligence publication does not equal operational takedown.

All defensive artifacts — IOCs, YARA rules, Sigma rules, and MITRE ATT&CK mappings — are released under TLP:WHITE with MIT license and are provided in the appendices below.

References

- [1] Unit 42 / Palo Alto Networks, “Iranian APT Targets Israeli Civilians with Fake Rocket Alert App,” March 4, 2026.
- [2] CloudSEK ThreatIntel, “RedAlert Trojan: Iranian APT Abusing Rocket Alert App to Target Israelis,” March 3, 2026.
- [3] Cloudflare Cloudforce One, “Operation Epic Fury: Android Campaign Threat Intelligence,”

March 4, 2026.

- [4] ClearSky Cyber Security, “False RedAlert APK Analysis,” March 2026.
- [5] Trellix Advanced Research Center, “Tracking Iranian Hactivist Operations,” March 2026.
- [6] Sophos X-Ops, “Threat Activity Update,” March 2026.
- [7] NetBlocks, “Iran Internet Connectivity Data, February 28, 2026,” netblocks.org.
- [8] BeyondTrust, “Infrastructure and Threat Advisory, February–March 2026.”
- [9] Hunt.io, “Infrastructure Correlation: AS36352 + NameCheap MuddyWater Pattern.”
- [10] SentinelOne SentinelLabs, “SpyC23: Android Surveillance Toolset — Arid Viper / APT-C-23 TTP Context,” 2023.

Verifiable technical data (direct links):

- [11] crt.sh — Certificate Transparency: `api.ra-backup.com` — CT record from June 23, 2025 (SOA serial 1750691767).
- [12] VirusTotal — LotAccessUI.EXE v3: SHA256 6209a952...8c12d6 — 13/72.
- [13] VirusTotal — LotAccessUI.EXE v1: SHA256 7d43d7f6...aad0d — first submission 2025-12-16, 4/65.
- [14] VirusTotal — RedAlert fake APK: SHA256 83651b05...78b72 — `com.red.alertx`.
- [15] VirusTotal — umgdn APK: SHA256 0cba66e7...a91e8 — `com.net.alerts` (undocumented at 2026-03-15).
- [16] GitHub — YARA rules, Sigma rules, IOC CSV (TLP:WHITE, MIT license): [paolocostanzo.github.io/operation-epic-fury-cyber-war-iran/](https://github.com/paolocostanzo/operation-epic-fury-cyber-war-iran/).

A. Indicators of Compromise (IOCs)

TLP:WHITE — Release: March 15, 2026 — License: MIT

All IPs defanged for safe publication. Restore dots for operational use.

```
# IP Addresses
216.45.58[.]148      # Windows C2 (primary)  -- HostPapa AS36352 Ashburn VA
167.160.187[.]43    # Windows C2 (backup)   -- RackNerd AS36352 Toronto CA
-- 0/94 VT

# Domains
api[.]ra-backup[.]com # Android + Windows C2 (primary, offline
post-takedown)
9732[.]5486311[.]xyz  # Windows C2 backup    -- 0/94 VT
```

```

# SHA256
6209a9524e97ee8ac5fb05668f2be9a18a455870bb8cf6022049ee8f458c12d6 #
  LotAccessUI v3
7d43d7f6c743912b74273901494ed18451aa2824130d9d405da250a9fe3aad0d #
  LotAccessUI v1
83651b0589665b112687f0858bfe2832ca317ba75e700c91ac34025ee6578b72 #
  RedAlert fake APK
0cba66e78ddaecfdd462c8cb39e443d083dc58c609b0edc73e8101e59ca91e8 # umgdn
  APK (undoc.)

# LotAccess v3 forensic hashes
MD5:      58dad3a41691265128c751d133d5525f
Imphash:  d89625bf08b621847b3ab97338a84dda # PE family pivot
JARM:     21d14d00021d21d00042d43d00041dd0fae37a26d202d4ca73c3c7b57c5a55

# Windows artifacts
Mutex:    tqvpn-gui-keep-one-instance # zero false positives
RegKey:   HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess\firstServer
RegKey:   HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess\secondServer
Path:     %TEMP%\EB93A6\cloudvpn.cfg
Path:     %TEMP%\EB93A6\ca.crt
Task:     Microsoft-Windows-DiskDiagnosticDataCollector # if pointing to
          %TEMP%

# Android packages
com.red.alertx # RedAlert fake stage 1
com.net.alerts # umgdn stage 2 (undocumented)

```

B. YARA Detection Rule

```

/*
  Rule:      IranianAPT_LotAccess_EXE_2026
  Author:    Paolo Costanzo - paolocostanzo.github.io
  TLP:      WHITE | License: MIT
  Ref:      paolocostanzo.github.io/operation-epic-fury-cyber-war-iran/
*/

rule IranianAPT_LotAccess_EXE_2026 {
  meta:
    description = "LotAccess trojanized AppEx VPN - Operation Epic
  Fury 2026"
    author      = "Paolo Costanzo - paolocostanzo.github.io"

```

```

date          = "2026-03-15"
tlp           = "WHITE"
hash_v3       = "6209a9524e97...ee8f458c12d6"
mitre_attack  = "T1071.001, T1497.003, T1053.005, T1036.007, T1112,
T1059.007"
confidence    = "HIGH"

strings:
  $mutex       = "tqvpn-gui-keep-one-instance"      ascii wide
  $c2_primary  = "216.45.58.148"                    ascii wide
  $c2_backup   = "167.160.187.43"                   ascii wide
  $c2_host     = "api.ra-backup.com"                 ascii wide
  $cfg         = "cloudvpn.cfg"                      ascii wide
  $appex_api   = "/cgi-bin/d_device_action.py?ButtonDownSSLFile" ascii
wide

condition:
  uint16(0) == 0x5A4D    // MZ header
  and filesize < 5MB
  and (
    $mutex
    or ($c2_primary and $cfg)
    or ($c2_backup  and $cfg)
    or ($appex_api  and ($c2_primary or $c2_backup))
  )
}

```

The mutex `tqvpn-gui-keep-one-instance` is the highest-confidence detection indicator with zero expected false positives in enterprise environments. The original AppEx Networks VPN client is extremely rare outside its original Chinese enterprise deployment context.

C. Sigma Detection Rules

Rule	Level	Category	Notes
iranian_apt_lotaccess_mutex	HIGH	Windows Endpoint	Mutex tqvpn-gui-keep-one-instance
iranian_apt_lotaccess_registry	MEDIUM	Windows Registry	HKCU\Software\AppEx Networks\LotAccess
iranian_apt_lotaccess_c2_networ	HIGH	Network	IPs 216.45.58.x / 167.160.187.x
iranian_apt_smishing_apk_packa	HIGH	Mobile Android	com.red.alertx / com.net.alerts
iranian_apt_lotaccess_scheduled_	MEDIUM	Windows Task Scheduler	Microsoft-Windows-DiskDiagnosticD pointing to %TEMP%

Full Sigma YAML definitions are available at:

paolocostanzo.github.io/operation-epic-fury-cyber-war-iran/

D. MITRE ATT&CK Mapping

Technique	Tactic	Description
T1497.003	Defense Evasion	Time-Based Evasion: RDTSC CPU cycle measurement to detect VM — primary evasion mechanism
T1071.001	Command & Control	App Layer Protocol: C2 over HTTP/HTTPS via trojanized VPN client
T1112	Defense Evasion	Modify Registry: C2 IP addresses stored in AppEx Networks registry keys
T1036.007	Defense Evasion	Masquerading: Legitimate Chinese enterprise VPN binary used as malware carrier
T1053.005	Execution / Persistence	Scheduled Task: Microsoft-Windows-DiskDiagnosticDataCollector
T1059.007	Execution	Command & Scripting Interpreter: JavaScript (Android stage component)
T1432	Collection	Access Contact List (Android — com.red.alertx / com.net.alerts)
T1430	Collection	Location Tracking: GPS coordinates (Android component)
T1636.004	Collection	Protected User Data: SMS Messages (Android component)
T1584	Resource Development	Compromise Infrastructure: shirideitch.com (Israeli site, 2017)